

CONDITIONS FOR ORGANIZING ELEMENTARY CLASSES THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. Innovative changes in the educational process, the introduction of any innovation into the educational system directly through updating and changing the activity of the pedagogue-educator is an urgent issue of today's demand. The guaranteed result of education determines the efficiency and achievement of the goal. It can be seen that the closer the result is to the goal, the more effective the educational process is.

Key words: pedagogue, primary education, education, pedagogical technology, innovation, educational efficiency, culture, enlightenment.

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the requirements of today's rapidly developing era, many urgent tasks have arisen due to the need for a new approach to the content and structure of education in the face of changing modern school education. Now it is necessary to form and teach the skills of independent learning and striving to improve the acquired knowledge, not using traditional methods of education.

That is why it is necessary for the teacher to have professional skills, to know how to use new modern educational technologies that meet the requirements of the current era. The goal of the pedagogical activity of any subject teacher, especially primary education teachers, is to prepare students to become mature and well-rounded individuals required in modern society in the future, to become creative and ambitious people, and is to achieve modern education.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of the use of pedagogical technologies by pedagogues-teachers of primary education in schools is of urgent importance, because the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the work of an educational institution is the most important condition for improving and reforming the school education system.

It is known that the initial foundations of personality development and literacy are laid in primary classes. Elementary school students develop their reading skills and abilities in elementary school, so this period is important in a person's life. The methodological basis of modern education is as follows [2]:

- systematic-active;
- project-research activities in education;
- Competent and axiological approach standards.

The systematic-active approach affects the educational results, in which the development of the student's personality is based on universal learning activities, understanding and mastering the world. The content of education is achieved through the method of organizing educational activities.

The qualities that must be manifested in the personality of a modern primary education teacher can be categorized as follows [3]:

1. professional qualities;
2. organizational qualities;
3. Qualities of accessibility to communication;
4. leadership qualities of the student team;
5. managerial qualities;
6. working qualities;
7. qualities of being able to organize creative activities;
8. Qualities of being able to correctly assess reality;
9. research qualities.

RESULTS

A modern primary education teacher (pedagogue) must be able to master the following creative-practical (constructive) skills:

- formation of integrated educational and educational material using separate information;
- enrichment of educational material with various pictures, photos, tables, diagrams, models, etc.;
- preparation of unique, original educational material;
- independent justification of a new method;
- instructions for training (lesson) and educational event
- creating a set of weapons;
- creating a technological passport, map of a lesson or educational event;
- creation of multimedia materials for use in a lesson or educational event;
- preparation of the presentation version of the educational material;
- creating videos with the active participation of students for educational events on various topics;
- preparation of lesson outline;
- development of test tasks based on different forms and methods (question, task, problem, example, exercise, test), assessment criteria;
- a creative approach to the organization of control work.

It is necessary for the teacher to present unexpected impressions to the students with his creativity in each subject, to bring them into the world of science in the true sense. For this, he must continue to search. For example, popular pedagogical methods include "intellectual competition", "ideal discussion", "analysis and description", "spreading and summarizing", etc. the introduction of such methods into the teaching process gives the expected results.

Intellectual competition - in this method, training is based on intellectual competition and debate of students. By means of the competition, students understand and consolidate a new topic. Winning and losing teams will be evaluated. This method is important because it increases students' ability to think scientifically.

Ideological discussion - in this method, during the training, students conduct an ideological-ideological discussion. They express their opinions on the subject of the training. Among them, the most clear, impartial and correct opinions are approved. A final conclusion is drawn based on the discussions. This method forms students' skills to defend, promote and

convince others of their opinions. This method is more important in the present era and is an important factor in educating the young generation on the basis of ideological and ideological immunity from the lower class.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The methods of analysis and description, dissemination and summation also form students' independent work, evaluation of their work and critical attitude.

In addition to these, it is desirable to organize methods and tools based on the uniqueness of the sciences. For example, the activities in the reading classes are called "Fairy tale within a fairy tale"; visual art classes "Walk to the Kingdom of Colors"; organization of mother-tongue classes on topics such as "joyful letters and soft sounds", and literature classes on topics such as "Heroes with us" will increase students' interest and passion for science. Also, the purity and grandeur of the motto chosen for each new lesson inspires and motivates students towards a new topic. For example: "Courageous and together for knowledge!", "Read, search, achieve the goal!", "Follow your desire" motivate students at the very beginning of the lesson.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, when applying interactive methods to the educational process, the teacher is in the role of manager of the educational process, in which the goal of management is directed to the student as the object and subject of education. So, the educational content of pedagogical technology is formed on the basis of methods, forms and tools. This process is aimed at achieving a guaranteed result. In short, solving the above-mentioned problems of modern general education schools, in particular, primary school education, is an urgent task of our time.

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